

DESIGN OF COMPACT UWB CIRCULAR MICROSTRIP PATCH ANTENNA USING ANN AND ANFIS SOFT COMPUTING TECHNIQUES

Rakesh K. Maurya¹, Reena Pant², Prakash C. Mishra³, Ajay K. Maurya⁴, Shakti P. Senapati⁵

^{1,2,3}Faculty of Engineering & Technology, MJP, Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, UP-243006, INDIA

⁴UNS, Institute of Engineering & Technology, VBS, Purvanchal University, Jaunpur, U.P-222001, INDIA

⁵Darbhangha College of Engineering, Darbhanga, Bihar-846005, INDIA

E-mail: rkm96ei42@gmail.com, reenapantbly@gmail.com, pmishrapso075@gmail.com,
ajaybtech84@gmail.com, shaktisenapati183@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT: A novel compact circular microstrip patch antenna (CCMPA) with DGS for UWB application is proposed for C, X, Ku and Ka-bands. For designing of UWB CCMPA an approach for optimizing the physical parameter, two robust techniques namely artificial neural network (ANN) and adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) are used. Commercially available Ansoft HFSS v.13 is utilized to extract the 144 data sets of CCMPAs having different sensitive parameters related to antenna dimensions and substrate materials. Apart from 144 simulated data sets, 129 were used for training and remaining 15 were utilized for testing of ANN and ANFIS model. The average percentage errors (APE) for first (f_1) and last (f_2) resonant frequency of return loss are calculated regarding performance of tested data sets of ANN and ANFIS model. The APE in ANN and ANFIS model are found in testing of resonant frequency f_1 and f_2 are 0.8731, 0.0699 and 0.7698, 0.0607 respectively. The very low error indicates that the models can be successfully applied for optimization of physical parameter of UWB CCMPA for computer aided design (CAD) applications. The trained ANN and ANFIS model can be used effectively for antenna parameter estimation, instead of running HFSS repetitively or other optimization techniques, which takes more time. Successful implementation of CCMPA shows broader impedance bandwidth of 2.6 GHz to 53.3 as 180% at 26 GHz of centre frequency. Average gain and -3 dB beam width of the proposed antenna is found 4.14 dBi. The proposed antenna can be effectively used in C, X, Ku and Ka-band applications.

INDEX TERMS- Compact Circular UWB microstrip Patch antenna, artificial neural network, adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system, CAD

Corresponding Author: Reena Pant

Email: reenapantbly@gmail.com

I. INTRODUCTION

Need of miniaturization and bandwidth enhancement of microstrip patch antenna (MPA) is today's challenge of researcher's, due to portability and uniqueness of MPA which covers maximum bands of communication applications. In this regard, many of researchers used substrate material with high dielectric constant in traditional MPA, and have been achieved miniaturisation but the bandwidth and efficiency is decreased [1-3]. Many of them has been tried to overcome this problem by applying slit/slot loading MPA [4-9], sorting pins [10-12], sorting walls [13], slot loaded patch [14-16] in traditional MPA and somehow success to reduce the size but not even more for bandwidth enhanced. For bandwidth enhancement the DGS MPA has been recently investigated [17-20] and the bandwidth enhancement up to 90% has been achieved. To achieve compactness and/or bandwidth enhancement in the designing of traditional MPA the analysis techniques such as cavity model [21] and transmission line model [22] is used. But the complicated shapes of MPA can't be analyzed with these traditional techniques. Hence some other powerful techniques such as method of moment [23] and finite difference time domain method [24] are used. But again these techniques, involves rigorous mathematical formulation with extensive numerical procedure hence, also more time consuming. In most of previous efforts some of them tried to design UWB MPA by these parametric analyses, and they have altered the parameter accordingly and achieved UWB characteristics [25-29]. Nowadays most powerful software such as IE3D, HFSS, CST Studio, is widely used for analysis of any type of antenna and other microwave structure with trial and error basis [5, 10, 17-20]. Hence again more time consuming and has no guaranteed to achieve a desirable goal even after numerous trial.

Recently ANN, ANFIS and/or SVM soft computing techniques have been used efficiently for analysis of any types of MPA without any rigorous mathematical calculation and time consumption. Because once a model of ANN, ANFIS or SVM has been designed for a MPA then it can be used many times at no time cost. Many of researcher [30-37] have been successfully used the ANN, ANFIS and SVM to analyse the various parameter of MPAs and design the model.

In this paper a Compact (20mm×20mm) UWB Antenna for C, X, Ku and Ka-Band application are modelled followed by parametric analysis with the help of ANN and ANFIS soft computing techniques. The basic design procedure/topology of ANN and ANFIS model for proposed MPA is shown in fig. 1. ANN and ANFIS model is design to compute the accurate resonant frequencies (the 1st resonant frequency f_1 and last resonant frequency f_2 of UWB) of proposed UWB CCMPA. To design the ANN and ANFIS model, 144 data sets were collected with the help of commercially available Ansoft HFSSv.13.

Fig. 1 Basic design procedure of ANN and ANFIS model for proposed UWB CCMPA

Hence the paper work is divided in next four parts: antenna structure and data collection by using HFSS v.13, then modeling of ANN and ANFIS for computing resonant frequencies using simulated data sets, after that discussion of results and in last results are concluded.

II. ANTENNA STRUCTURE AND SIMULATION

Fig.2 exhibits the configuration of compact (20mm*20mm) UWB microstrip feed CCMPA. The MPA is consist of a circular patch of radius r tapered with angle ϕ with two symmetrical slot of $w_s \times l_s$ at feed side, etched onto a dielectric substrate (20mm×20mm) of thickness h , loss tangent of $\tan \delta$ and relative permittivity of ϵ_r . An open ended microstrip line (50-Ω) feed of width $w_f \times l_f$ is placed on opposite side of the ground plane. The ground is defected with rectangular size of 6mm×20mm is taken at the opposite of feed as shown in fig.. In proposed MPA we have applied three techniques to achieve UWB antenna i.e. two symmetrical slots on circular patch, tapering the patch and a partial ground plane.

In order to determine the values of f_1 and f_2 of UWB for ANN and ANFIS model, the simulation is performed by HFSS v.13. The 144 CCMPAs having various sets of sensitive parameters of antenna dimensions and substrate material are listed in table 1. These sets of UWB CCMPA operate in band width of 2.3-53.5 GHz to 3.4-54.6 GHz corresponding in C, X, Ku, and Ka-bands.

Fig. 2 Proposed Geometry of UWB CCMPA

Table 1: 144 physical and electrical parametric sets of simulated UWB CCMPAs

Number of Simulation Sets	Physical and electrical parameters					
	r (mm)	l_s (mm)	w_s (mm)	ϕ (degree)	h (mm)	ϵ_r
18+18=36	4.5	1.5 1.8	1.3 1.6	10, 15, 20	0.8, 1.6	2.2,2.33,4.4
18+18=36	5.0	1.8 2.0	2.0 2.0	15, 20, 25	0.8, 2.5	2.33,4.4,6.15
18+18=36	5.5	2.1 2.4	1.9 2.2	10, 15, 25	1.6, 3.2	2.2,4.4,6.15
18+18=36	6.0	2.4 2.7	2.2 2.5	20, 25, 30	3.2, 2.5	2.33,4.4,6.15

III. DESIGN OF ANN AND ANFIS MODEL

(a) Design procedure of ANN Model

ANN is one of the most intelligent, fast and flexible tool to model nonlinear relation, simulation, and optimization of antenna [38]. ANN based CAD model are much popular due to their accuracy in results, ability and adaptability to learn, least information requirement, quick real time response and simple implementation feature. For the best model for a particular problem many of basic parameters of ANN is settled on trial and error basis. The basic parameters of ANN are: network architecture, hidden layers, neurons in hidden layer, learning algorithm, activation functions etc. Two special class of ANN architecture, Multi-layer Perceptron (MLPs) [39] and Radial-basis Function Networks (RBFNs) [40] have been widely used to analysis this type of problem. In this paper MLP network architecture is used. An MLP consist with three types of layers: an input layer, an output layer and one or more hidden layers. The results of MLPs for a particular problem depend on the use of learning algorithm. After several trials, the Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) algorithm is found suitable for

this MPA. The accurate ANN-synthesis model needed a suitable number of neurons in hidden layers. For proper configuration of hidden layers of proposed model, many experiments were carried out. After many trials, by changing the epoch, neurons and activation functions in layers, high accuracy is achieved using MLP with two hidden layered network. Hence, the model has total 4 layers (two hidden layers, one input layer and one output layer). The best suitable network configuration were found 6×28×12×2, mean that the number of neurons are 6,28,12,2 in Input layer, 1st, 2nd hidden layers, and output layer respectively. The linear activation function is found suitable in input and output layer, tangent sigmoid activation function is found suitable in hidden layers. Initial weights of ANN model are set up randomly. The weights adoption used mean square error (MSE) between target and output of ANN. The training epochs was found 543 for accurate model. Finally the accurate ANN model for UWB CCMPA is shown in fig. 3.

Fig. 3 ANN model of proposed UWB CCMPA

The accuracy of ANN-based analysis model is depends on training data sets used during training. More and more data sets give more accurate result. Now the collected data sets were arranged in six-row input matrix (r , l_s , w_s , ϕ , h , and ϵ_r) and two-row target matrix (f_1 and f_2). Before training, the data sets were scaled in $[-1, +1]$ to each row of input as well as output matrix for easier learning process. A neural network model is developed by learning through training. Training process minimize the training error between the target output and the output of ANN. The training error is checked by MSE performance graph. In the training, when MSE is found near to zero, then training process stopped and the model is ready. The trained model then validated by test inputs of 15 remaining input data sets, which is already extracted by HFSS v.13. Then APE of test output of model is calculated and shown in table 2. The formula for the calculation of APE is:

$$APE = \frac{\sum |(f_{HFSS} - f_{ANN/ANFIS}) / f_{HFSS}|}{number_of_antenna} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

(b) Design Procedure of ANFIS Model

ANFIS is an universal estimator [41] it combines the benefits of ANN and fuzzy inference system (FIS) in a single model. FIS is a computing tool, based on fuzzy set theory, fuzzy if then rules and fuzzy reasoning. The membership function (MF) parameters of fuzzy system have been tuned using neuro-adaptive learning methods similar to those used in training of neural networks. Hence, ANFIS is FIS implementation in the framework of an adaptive fuzzy neural network, which is a very powerful approach for analyzing complex and nonlinear relationship of input and output data sets. The ANFIS architecture of proposed MPA is shown in fig. 4, which is consist of 5 steps: inputs, input membership functions, fuzzy rules, output membership functions, and outputs.

Fig. 4 ANFIS model of proposed UWB CCMPA

For the best model for a particular problem many of basic parameters of ANFIS is also settled on trial and error basis. After many trials in training of 129 input-output data sets (same data sets used in training of ANN) the following parameter of ANFIS model is found suitable for proposed MPA. These suitable ANFIS parameters are: ANFIS model type- Sugeno, input/output MF type- Gaussson/Linear, number of MFs-38, number of fuzzy rules-38, training epochs-122. Again as in ANN, after design the model remaining 15 input data sets were used to test the trained model. Output/target is not used in testing, but the tested results are compared with target and calculated APE. The APE of test output of ANFIS model is calculated and are also shown in table 2.

Table 2: The comparative results of HFSS (simulation), ANN and ANFIS model for UWB CCMPA

Test patches	Input dimensions (mm)						Results (GHz)					
	r	l _s	w _s	φ	h	ε _r	HFSS		ANN		ANFIS	
							f ₁	f ₂	f ₁	f ₂	f ₁	f ₂
1	4.5	1.5	1.3	15	0.8	4.4	4.582	46.552	4.540	46.577	4.555	46.578
2	4.5	1.8	1.6	10	0.8	2.33	4.625	46.992	4.657	46.967	4.651	46.971
3	4.5	1.8	1.6	20	1.6	2.2	5.071	47.417	5.112	47.389	5.109	47.392
4	5.0	1.8	2.0	15	0.8	2.33	4.937	46.148	4.965	46.179	4.961	46.175
5*	5.0	2.0	2.0	15	0.8	4.4	4.900	46.660	4.677	46.598	4.674	46.591
6	5.0	1.8	2.0	20	2.5	2.33	6.884	48.588	6.851	48.551	6.855	48.557
7	5.0	2.0	2.0	20	0.8	6.15	6.422	48.225	6.449	48.258	6.446	48.252
8	5.0	2.0	2.0	25	2.5	6.15	5.871	47.844	5.845	47.877	5.850	47.869
9	5.5	2.1	1.9	10	1.6	4.4	6.461	48.692	6.497	48.728	6.490	48.722
10	5.5	2.1	1.9	25	3.2	2.2	5.818	47.567	5.839	47.592	5.836	47.588
11	5.5	2.4	2.2	15	1.6	6.15	3.229	45.094	3.253	45.125	3.251	45.119
12	5.5	2.4	2.2	15	3.2	2.2	3.466	45.347	3.497	45.312	3.492	45.323
13	6.0	2.4	2.2	20	2.5	4.4	4.893	47.495	4.862	47.471	4.873	47.473
14	6.0	2.7	2.5	30	2.5	4.4	6.056	48.884	6.089	48.850	6.081	48.857
15	6.0	2.7	2.5	25	3.2	6.15	5.990	47.503	5.961	47.539	5.967	47.533
Average Percentage Error (APE)									0.8731	0.0699	0.7698	0.0607
* the data set for which fig.5 and fig.6 is plotted												

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The concert of trained ANN and ANFIS model is tested for left over 15 input data samples. The 15 input constraint and their simulated results and results of ANN and ANFIS model are given in table 2. So as to observe the accuracy and constancy of the proposed ANN and ANFIS model, APE of 1st and last resonant frequency for 15 tested samples are calculated and also given in table 2. It is observed from results, ANN and ANFIS model successfully obtained the resonant frequency. The APE of ANN and ANFIS model are of resonant frequency f₁ and f₂ are 0.8731, 0.0699 and 0.7698, 0.0607 respectively. Therefore the results of ANN and ANFIS model are much close to the simulated results.

A simulated S_{11} (return loss Vs frequency variation) plot of a random selected data set (sl. No. 4 highlighted in table 2) are shown in fig. 5. It can be seen that antenna has a UWB performance of 51 GHz (2.6-53.5 GHz) impedance BW below 10 dB of return loss. The simulated gain with frequency variation plot of this data set is also shown in Fig. 6. The average gain of antenna is 4.15 dBi and it can be seen that the gain of projected data set is nearly stable over the entire impedance bandwidth. Therefore, the ANN and ANFIS soft computing techniques can be effectively used for design of the proposed MPA without any complicated mathematical and complicated trials. In addition the proposed soft computing techniques, it can be modified or improved for similar tasks of nonlinear electromagnetic problems. Hence, the proposed ANN and ANFIS model for proposed UWB CCMPAs analysis are more versatile than other complicated methods used in various literatures.

Fig. 5 Simulated return loss vs frequency plot of proposed UWB CCMPA

Fig. 6 Simulated gain vs frequency plot of proposed UWB CCMPA

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper ANN and ANFIS model have been successfully introduced for the analysis of UWB CCMPA. The measured and simulated results agreed the validity of ANN and ANFIS results. The HFSS, ANN, and ANFIS results are shown in table 2. The results shown in table 2 are enough to verify the proposed ANN and ANFIS model. Here I want to clarify that; the better results may be obtained by choosing other training and test data sets from the ones used in this paper, or by collecting more data sets values for training.

REFERENCES

- [1] Garg R, Bhartia P, Bahl I, Ittipihoon A. (2001). *Microstrip antenna design handbook*. London: Artech House.
- [2] Wong K. 2002. *Compact and broadband microstrip antennas*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- [3] Kumar G, Ray K.P. (2003). *Broadband microstrip antennas*. USA: Artech House.
- [4] Deshmukh A.A., Kumar G. (2007). Formulation of resonant frequency for compact rectangular microstrip antennas. *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*; 49(2), 498-502.
- [5] Gautam A. K., Kanaujia B. K. (2013). A novel dual band asymmetric slit with defected ground structure for circular polarization operation. *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*; 55, 1198-1202.
- [6] Ooi B. L., Shen Q. (2000). A novel E-shaped broadband microstrip patch antenna. *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*, 27(5), 348-353.
- [7] Sheta A. F., Mohra A., Mahmoud S. F. (1982). Multi-band operation of a compact H-shaped microstrip antenna. *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*, 35, 363-368.
- [8] Chew W. (1982). A broad-band annular-ring microstrip antenna. *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, 30(5), 918-923.
- [9] Wong K. L., Pan S. C. (1997) Compact triangular microstrip antenna. *Electron. Lett.*, 33, 433-435.
- [10] Khandelwal M. K., Kanaujia B. K., Dwari S., Kumar S., Gautam A. K. (2014). Analysis and design of wide band microstrip-line-fed antenna with defected ground structure for Ku band application. *INT. J. Electron. Commun (AEU)*, 68, 951-958.
- [11] Wong K. L., Chen W. S. (1997). Compact microstrip antenna with dual-frequency operation. *Electron. Lett.*, 33, 646-648.
- [12] Pan S. C., Wong K. L. (1997). Dual-frequency triangular microstrip antenna with a shorting pin. *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propagat.*, 45, 1889-1892.
- [13] Guo Y. X., Luk K. M., Lee K. F. (1999). L-probe proximity-fed short-circuited patch antenna. *Electron. Lett.*, 35, 2069-2071.
- [14] Wong K. L., Yang K. P. (1998). Compact dual-frequency microstrip antenna with a pair of bent slots. *Electron. Lett.*, 34, 225-227.
- [15] Chen W. S., Wu C. K., Wong K. L. (1998). Compact circularly polarized microstrip antenna with bent slots. *Electron. Lett.*, 34, 1278-1280.
- [16] Saxena S., Kanaujia B. K., Dwari S., Kumar S., Tiwari R. (2017). A Compact microstrip fed dual polarized multiband antenna for IEEE 802.11 a/b/g/n/ac/ax applications. *Int. J. Electron. Commun. (AEU)*, 72, 95-103.
- [17] Gautam A. K., Yadav S., Kanaujia B.K. (2013). A CPW-Fed compact UWB Microstrip antenna. *IEEE Antenna and wireless propagation letter*, 12, 151-157.
- [18] Chiang K. H., Tam K. W. (2008). Microstrip monopole antenna with enhanced bandwidth using defected ground structure. *IEEE Antennas Wirel. Propag. Lett.*, 7, 532-536.
- [19] Chen D. C. and Wong K. L. (1995), "Input impedance and radiation pattern of a probe-fed cylindrical annular-ring microstrip antenna," *Microwave Opt. Technol. Lett.*, vol. 8, pp. 152-156.
- [20] Kishore N., Prakash A., Tripathi V. S. (2017). A reconfigurable ultra-wide with defected ground structure for ITS application. *Int. J. Electron. Commun (AEU)*, 72, 210-216.
- [21] Richards W. F., Lo Y. T., Hirisson D. D. (1981). An improved theory for microstrip antenna application. *IEEE Transaction Antenn. Propag.*, 29, 84-87.
- [22] Bhattacharya K., Garg R. (1985). A generalized transmission line model for microstrip patches. *IEE Proc. Microwave Antenna Propag.*, 132, 93-99.
- [23] Harrington R. F. (1993). *Field Computation by moment method*. Piscataway NJ: IEEE Press.
- [24] Taflove A. (1995). *Computational electrodynamics*. The finite difference time domain. Boston: Artech House.
- [25] Liang J. X, Chiau C. C, Chen X. D, Parini C. G. (2005). Study of a printed circular disc monopole antenna for UWB systems. *IEEE Transaction on Antennas and Propagation*, 53 (11), 3500-3505.
- [26] John M., Ammann M. J. (2005). Optimization of impedance bandwidth for the printed rectangular monopole antenna. *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*, 47(2), 153-155.
- [27] Eldek A. A. (2006). Numerical analyses of a small ultra wideband microstrip-fed tap monopole antenna. *Progress in Electromagnetic Research*, 65, 59-69.
- [28] Fallahi R., Kalteh A. A., Roozbahani M. G. (2008). A novel UWB elliptical slot antenna with band-notched characteristics. *Progress in Electromagnetic Research*, 82, 127-137.
- [29] Sadat M., Houshmand M., Roshandel M. (2007). Design of a microstrip square-ring slot antenna filled by an H-shaped slot for UWB applications. *Progress in Electromagnetics Research*, 70, 191-199.

- [30] Akdagli A., Toktas A., Kayabasi A., Develi I. (2013). An application of artificial neural network to compute the resonant frequency of E-shaped compact microstrip antennas. *Journal of Electrical Engineering Elektrotechnicky Casopis*, 64(5), 317-323.
- [31] Khan T., De A. (2013). A generalized ANN model for analyzing and synthesizing rectangular, circular, and triangular microstrip antennas. *Hindawi Publishing Corporation, Chinese journal of engineering volume, article id 647191*, 1-9.
- [32] Guney K., Sarikaya N. (2007). A hybrid method based on combining artificial neural network and fuzzy inference system for simultaneous computation of resonant frequencies of rectangular, circular and triangular microstrip antennas. *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and propagation*, 55, 659-669.
- [33] Maurya R. K., Vijay, Mishra S., Chaudhary N., Kumar D. (2013). Model for calculation of patch radius of circular microstrip antenna using artificial neural network, *IEEE Int. Conf. DOI 10.1109/ICMIRA*, 39, 167-174.
- [34] Song H. J., Miao C. Y., Shen Z. Q., Roel W., Maja D. H., Francky C. (2010). Design of fuzzy cognitive maps using neural networks for predicting chaotic time series. *Neural Networks*, 23(10), 264-275.
- [35] Wang Z. B., Fang S. J., Wang Q., Liu H. M. (2012). An ANN based synthesis model for the single-feed circularly-polarized square microstrip antenna with truncated corners. *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, 60, 5989-5993.
- [36] T. N. Kapetanakis, I. O. Vardiambasis, E. I. Lourakis and A. Maras (2018). "Applying Neuro-Fuzzy Soft Computing Techniques to the Circular Loop Antenna Radiation Problem," in *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 17, no. 9, pp. 1673-1676, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2018.2862939.
- [37] Kayabasi A., Akdagli A. (2015). Predicting the resonant frequency of E-shaped compact microstrip antennas by using ANFIS and SVM. *Wireless Pers. Commun.*, 82, 1893-1906.
- [38] Zhang Q. J., Gupta K. C. (2000). *Neural network for RF and microwave design*. Artech House: Norwood, Mass, USA.
- [39] Ubeyli E.D., Guler I. (2004). Multilayer perceptron neural network to compute quasistatic parameter of asymmetric coplanar waveguides. *Neurocomputing*, 62, 349-365.
- [40] Mishra R. K., Patnaik A. (1998). Neural network based CAD model for the design of square patch antennas. *IEEE Transactions on Antenna and Propagation*, 46, 1890-1892.
- [41] Jang, Sun, Mizutani. (1997). *Neuro-Fuzzy and Soft Computing*. Prentice Hall, 335-368.